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First optimal vectorial eighth-order iterative scheme for solving non-linear systems

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ABSTRACT

We introduce a novel iterative method achieving eighth-order convergence, establishing its optimality for solving non-linear systems. A rigorous analysis of convergence order is presented, complemented by investigations into both efficiency indices and the complex dynamics of the proposed method. To assess its performance, extensive numerical experiments are conducted, facilitating comparative analysis with established methods from the literature.

1. Introduction and design of the new iterative process

Numerous problems in different fields of science and engineering require the solution of systems of nonlinear equations. It is well known that, in general, there are no analytical procedures to find the exact solutions, so we must resort to iterative processes that approximate such solutions.

Newton's procedure, a cornerstone of numerical analysis (see [1]), is defined for vectorial problems as follows:

$$x^{(k+1)} = x^{(k)} - [F'(x^{(k)})]^{-1} F(x^{(k)}), \quad k = 0, 1, 2, \dots, \quad (1)$$

being $F : W \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ a non-linear function describing the system of equations $F(x) = 0$, and $F'(x)$ its associated Jacobian matrix. Known for its quadratic convergence and computational efficiency, Newton's method has served as a benchmark for the development of numerous iterative methods published in recent years with the goal of improving the convergence order, without substantially increasing computational cost and expanding the sets of initial approximations that lead to the convergence of the method (see, for example, the manuscripts [2–5], the book [6] and the references therein).

Furthermore, according to a conjecture proposed in [7], Newton's method stands as the first optimal vectorial procedure for solving systems of non-linear equations:

Conjecture 1. *Any Newton-type iterative method for solving non-linear systems, without memory, has an order of convergence that cannot exceed $2^{k_1+k_2-2}$, where k_1 is the number of functional evaluations in the entries of the Jacobian matrix per iteration and k_2 is the number of functional evaluations of the non-linear function, which where $k_1 \leq k_2$. If the method reaches this bound, it is called optimal in the vectorial sense.*

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To the best of our knowledge, only one parametric class of optimal schemes for vectorial models, in accordance with the aforementioned conjecture, has been documented in the literature ([8]). In this work, the authors introduced a family of optimal vectorial fourth-order methods depending on two parameters, characterized by

$$\begin{cases} y^{(k)} &= x^{(k)} - [F'(x^{(k)})]^{-1} F(x^{(k)}), \\ x^{(k+1)} &= y^{(k)} - [F'(x^{(k)})]^{-1} (p_k F(y^{(k)}) + q_k F(x^{(k)})), \quad k = 0, 1, 2, \dots \end{cases} \tag{2}$$

where

$$v_k = \frac{\|F(y^{(k)})\|_2}{\|F(x^{(k)})\|_2}, \quad K_k = \frac{1}{1 + \lambda v_k}, \quad p_k = K_k(1 + \psi v_k), \quad q_k = 2K_k v_k.$$

The use of the variable v_k was introduced in [9]. Family (2) exhibits fourth-order convergence. Our primary objective is to develop an optimal method with an eighth-order convergence. Additionally, we aim to perform these modifications without significantly adding computational cost, to obtain a competitive and efficient method comparable to other existing schemes with similar structure. To achieve this objective, we select the member of family (2) corresponding to $\lambda = 0$ and $\psi = 1$, an additional iterative step is implemented, and new accelerating scalar functions, similar to v_k , are incorporated. The resulting three-steps method, which we denote as CTT (3), is subsequently defined as follows:

$$\begin{cases} z^{(k)} &= y^{(k)} - [F'(x^{(k)})]^{-1} ((1 + v_k)F(y^{(k)}) + 2v_k F(x^{(k)})), \\ x^{(k+1)} &= z^{(k)} - [F'(x^{(k)})]^{-1} (F(z^{(k)}) + (2\alpha_k(1 - v_k) + 4\delta_k) F(x^{(k)}) + (2\alpha_k + \beta_k)F(y^{(k)})), \end{cases} \tag{3}$$

where $y^{(k)}$ is a Newton's step and the accelerators are

$$\begin{cases} v_k = \frac{F(y^{(k)})^T F(y^{(k)})}{F(x^{(k)})^T F(x^{(k)})}, & \alpha_k = \frac{F(y^{(k)})^T F(z^{(k)})}{F(x^{(k)})^T F(x^{(k)})}, \\ \beta_k = \frac{F(z^{(k)})^T F(z^{(k)})}{F(y^{(k)})^T F(y^{(k)})}, & \delta_k = \frac{F(z^{(k)})^T F(z^{(k)})}{F(x^{(k)})^T F(x^{(k)})}. \end{cases}$$

This article is organized as follows. Section 1 provides an introduction and a novel iterative method specifically designed for solving non-linear systems. In Section 2, a rigorous mathematical analysis of the order of convergence of the proposed method is performed. It is shown that this method is optimal for non-linear systems, exhibiting impressive eighth-order convergence. In Section 3, a comprehensive analysis of the complex dynamics of the proposed method is conducted. This analysis investigates the stability and long-term behavior of the method in the complex plane, providing valuable insights into its robustness and potential limitations. Section 4 presents an efficiency study of the proposed scheme, comparing its performance with similar methods in the literature. In Section 5, a series of numerical experiments are performed to evaluate the behavior of the procedure, comparing its performance with other known iterative methods. Finally, Section 6 finishes with conclusions and future work, followed by a list of references.

2. Convergence analysis

The eighth-order convergence of the iterative scheme CTT (3) is formally established in the following result.

Theorem 1. *Let $F : W \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ be a nonlinear function, sufficiently differentiable, defined in a neighborhood of ξ , W , such that $F(\xi) = 0$. Also, let $F'(\xi)$ be non-singular. Therefore, $\{x^{(k)}\}$ generated by method CTT (3) converges to ξ with local order 8, where $x^{(0)}$ is an initial approximation near to ξ .*

Proof. Let us denote by $C_i = \frac{1}{i!} F'(\xi)^{-1} F^{(i)}(\xi)$, for $i \geq 2$, and the error at each step of iteration k as $e_k = x^{(k)} - \xi$, $e_{y,k} = y^{(k)} - \xi$ and $e_{z,k} = z^{(k)} - \xi$. Then, by expanding the non-linear function F and its Jacobian operator F' at iterate $x^{(k)}$ around ξ , we get

$$F(x^{(k)}) = F'(\alpha) (e_k + C_2 e_k^2 + C_3 e_k^3 + C_4 e_k^4 + C_5 e_k^5 + C_6 e_k^6 + C_7 e_k^7) + O(e_k^8),$$

and

$$F'(x^{(k)}) = F'(\xi) (I + 2C_2 e_k + 3C_3 e_k^2 + 4C_4 e_k^3 + 5C_5 e_k^4 + 6C_6 e_k^5 + 7C_7 e_k^6) + O(e_k^7).$$

Now, we express the Taylor development

$$[F'(x^{(k)})]^{-1} = (I + D_1 e_k + D_2 e_k^2 + D_3 e_k^3 + D_4 e_k^4 + D_5 e_k^5 + D_6 e_k^6) F'(\xi)^{-1},$$

we force $[F'(x^{(k)})]^{-1} F'(x^{(k)}) = I$, and therefore factors D_i are given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_1 &= -2C_2, \\
 D_2 &= -2D_1C_2 - 3C_3 = -3C_3 + 4C_2^2, \\
 D_3 &= -2D_2C_2 - 3D_1C_3 - 4C_4 = -4C_4 + 6C_2C_3 + 6C_3C_2 - 8C_2^3, \\
 D_4 &= -2D_3C_2 - 3D_2C_3 - 4D_1C_4 - 5C_5 \\
 &= -5C_5 + 8C_2C_4 + 9C_3^2 + 8C_4C_2 - 12C_2^2C_3 \\
 &\quad - 12C_2C_3C_2 - 12C_3C_2^2 + 16C_2^4, \\
 D_5 &= -2D_4C_2 - 3D_3C_3 - 4D_2C_4 - 5D_1C_5 - 6C_6, \\
 D_6 &= -2D_5C_2 - 3D_4C_3 - 4D_3C_4 - 5D_2C_5 - 6D_1C_6 - 7C_7.
 \end{aligned}$$

Then, the local error at the first step is

$$\begin{aligned}
 e_{y,k} &= y^{(k)} - \xi = x^{(k)} - \xi - [F'(x^{(k)})]^{-1} F(x^{(k)}) \\
 &= Y_2e_k^2 + Y_3e_k^3 + Y_4e_k^4 + Y_5e_k^5 + Y_6e_k^6 + Y_7e_k^7 + O(e_k^8),
 \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
 Y_2 &= -D_1 - C_2, \\
 Y_3 &= -D_2 - D_1C_2 - C_3, \\
 Y_4 &= -D_3 - D_2C_2 - D_1C_3 - C_4, \\
 Y_5 &= -D_4 - D_3C_2 - D_2C_3 - D_1C_4 - C_5, \\
 Y_6 &= -D_5 - D_4C_2 - D_3C_3 - D_2C_4 - D_1C_5 - C_6, \\
 Y_7 &= -D_6 - D_5C_2 - D_4C_3 - D_3C_4 - D_2C_5 - D_1C_6 - C_7,
 \end{aligned}$$

that, after replacement and simplification, yields to

$$\begin{aligned}
 Y_2 &= C_2, \\
 Y_3 &= 2C_3 - 2C_2^2, \\
 Y_4 &= 3C_4 - 4C_2C_3 - 3C_3C_2 + 4C_2^3, \\
 Y_5 &= 4C_5 + D_3C_2 + 2D_2C_3 + 3D_1C_4, \\
 Y_6 &= 5C_6 + D_4C_2 + 2D_3C_3 + 3D_2C_4 + 4D_1C_5, \\
 Y_7 &= 6C_7 + D_5C_2 + 2D_4C_3 + 3D_3C_4 + 4D_2C_5 + 5D_1C_6.
 \end{aligned}$$

Now we expand v_k . To achieve this, we expand function F at $y^{(k)}$ about ξ ,

$$F(y^{(k)}) = F'(\xi) \left(e_{y,k} + C_2e_{y,k}^2 + C_3e_{y,k}^3 + C_4e_{y,k}^4 \right) + O(e_{y,k}^5),$$

that is,

$$F(y^{(k)}) = F'(\alpha) \left(Y_2e_k^2 + Y_3e_k^3 + (Y_4 + C_2Y_2Y_2)e_k^4 + Y_{5,1}e_k^5 + Y_{6,1}e_k^6 + Y_{7,1}e_k^7 \right) + O(e_k^8),$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
 Y_{5,1} &= Y_5 + C_2(Y_2Y_2 + Y_2Y_3), \\
 Y_{6,1} &= Y_6 + C_2(Y_4Y_2 + Y_3Y_3 + Y_2Y_4) + C_3Y_2^3, \\
 Y_{7,1} &= Y_7 + C_2(Y_5Y_2 + Y_4Y_3 + Y_3Y_4 + Y_2Y_5) + C_3(Y_3Y_2 + Y_2Y_3).
 \end{aligned}$$

Let us remark that the factor $v_k = \frac{F(y^{(k)})^T F(y^{(k)})}{F(x^{(k)})^T F(x^{(k)})}$ is scalar in spite of the vectorial character of $F(x^{(k)})$ and $F(y^{(k)})$.

To manage it properly, Singh et al. in [9] expanded it as

$$\frac{F(y^{(k)})^T F(y^{(k)})}{F(x^{(k)})^T F(x^{(k)})} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n f_i^2(y^{(k)})}{\sum_{i=1}^n f_i^2(x^{(k)})},$$

being

$$f_i(x^{(k)}) = f'_i(\xi)e_k + \frac{1}{2}f''_i(\xi)e_k^2 + \frac{1}{6}f'''_i(\xi)e_k^3 + \frac{1}{24}f^{(iv)}_i(\xi)e_k^4 + O(e_k^5).$$

By denoting $J_i = f'_i(\xi)$, $H_i = \frac{1}{2}f''_i(\xi)$, $I_i = \frac{1}{6}f'''_i(\xi)$ and $N_i = \frac{1}{24}f^{(iv)}_i(\xi)$, we get

$$f_i^2(x^{(k)}) = J_i^T J_i e_k^2 + (J_i^T H_i + H_i^T J_i) e_k^3 + (J_i^T I_i + H_i^T H_i + I_i^T J_i) e_k^4 + (J_i^T N_i + H_i^T I_i + I_i^T H_i + N_i^T J_i) e_k^5 + O(e_k^6).$$

If we denote by

$$\begin{aligned} P &= \sum J_i^T J_i, \\ Q &= \sum J_i^T H_i + H_i^T J_i, \\ R &= \sum J_i^T I_i + H_i^T H_i + I_i^T J_i, \\ S &= \sum J_i^T N_i + H_i^T I_i + I_i^T H_i + N_i^T J_i, \end{aligned}$$

the accelerating factor v_k can be expanded as

$$v_k = \frac{F(y^{(k)})^T F(y^{(k)})}{F(x^{(k)})^T F(x^{(k)})} = \frac{Pe_k^2 + Qe_k^3 + Re_k^4 + Se_k^5 + O(e_k^6)}{Pe_k^2 + Qe_k^3 + Re_k^4 + Se_k^5 + O(e_k^6)}.$$

Note that, by definition, we can express $Q = PC_2 + C_2P$, $R = C_3P + C_2^2 + PC_3$ y $S = PC_4 + C_3C_2 + C_2C_3 + C_4P$. Then, by expanding $[F(x^{(k)})^T F(x^{(k)})]^{-1}$ as we did for $[F'(x^{(k)})]^{-1}$, we get

$$[F(x^{(k)})^T F(x^{(k)})]^{-1} = \frac{P^{-1}}{e_k^2} \left(1 - P^{-1}Qe_k + \left((P^{-1}Q)^2 - P^{-1}R \right) e_k^2 + \left(2(P^{-1})^2QR - (P^{-1}Q)^3 - P^{-1}S \right) e_k^3 + O(e_k^4) \right),$$

and then,

$$v_k = n_2e_k^2 + n_3e_k^3 + n_4e_k^4 + n_5e_k^5 + O(e_k^6),$$

being

$$\begin{aligned} n_2 &= C_2^2, \\ n_3 &= -P^{-1}QC_2^2 + 2C_2C_3 + 2C_3C_2 - 4C_2^3, \\ n_4 &= (P^{-1})^2Q^2C_2^2 - P^{-1}RC_2^2 - 2P^{-1}QC_2C_3 + 3C_2C_4 - 2P^{-1}QC_3C_2 + 4C_3^2 + 3C_4C_2 + P^{-1}QC_2^3 + 4P^{-1}QC_2^3 \\ &\quad - 8C_2^2C_3 - 7C_2C_3C_2 - 7C_3C_2^2 + 12C_2^4, \\ n_5 &= -(P^{-1})^3Q^3C_2^2 + 2(P^{-1})^2QRC_2^2 - P^{-1}SC_2^2 + 2(P^{-1})^2Q^2C_2C_3 - 2P^{-1}RC_2C_3 - 3P^{-1}QC_2C_4 + 2(P^{-1})^2Q^2C_3C_2 \\ &\quad - 2P^{-1}RC_3C_2 - 4P^{-1}QC_3^2 + 6C_3C_4 - 3P^{-1}QC_4C_2 + 6C_4C_3 - (P^{-1})^2Q^2C_2^3 - 4(P^{-1})^2Q^2C_2^3 + 4P^{-1}RC_2^3 \\ &\quad + 8P^{-1}QC_2^2C_3 - 6C_2^2C_4 + 7P^{-1}QC_2C_3C_2 - 8C_2C_3^2 + 7P^{-1}QC_3C_2^2 - 14C_3C_2C_3 - 6C_3^2C_2 \\ &\quad - 6C_4C_2^2 - 12P^{-1}QC_2^4 + 16C_2^3C_3 + 6C_2^2C_3C_2 + 8C_2C_3C_2^2 + 14C_3C_2^3 - 16C_2^5. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, the expansion of the error at the second step is

$$\begin{aligned} e_{z,k} &= z^{(k)} - \xi = y^{(k)} - \xi - [F'(x^{(k)})]^{-1} \left((1 + v_k)F(y^{(k)}) + 2v_kF(x^{(k)}) \right) \\ &= e_{y,k} - (I + D_1e_k + D_2e_k^2 + D_3e_k^3 + D_4e_k^4 + D_5e_k^5 + D_6e_k^6) (Y_2e_k^2 + (n_2 + Y_3)e_k^3 + (n_3 + 2n_2C_2 + Y_4 + C_2Y_2^2)e_k^4 \\ &\quad + (n_4 + 2n_3C_2 + n_2(3C_3 - 2C_2^2) + Y_{5,1})e_k^5 + (n_5 + 2n_4C_2 + n_3(3C_3 - 2C_2^2) + n_2(Y_4 + C_2Y_2Y_2 + C_4) + Y_{6,1})e_k^6) + O(e_k^7) \\ &= e_{y,k} - (Y_2e_k^2 + (n_2 + Y_3 + D_1Y_2)e_k^3 + (n_3 + 2n_2C_2 + Y_4 + C_2Y_2^2 + D_1(n_2 + Y_3) + D_2Y_2)e_k^4 \\ &\quad + (n_4 + 2n_3C_2 + n_2(3C_3 - 2C_2^2) + Y_{5,1} + D_1(n_3 + 2n_2C_2 + Y_4 + C_2Y_2^2) + D_2(n_2 + Y_3) + D_3Y_2)e_k^5 \\ &\quad + (n_5 + 2n_4C_2 + n_3(3C_3 - 2C_2^2) + n_2(Y_4 + C_2Y_2Y_2 + C_4) + Y_{6,1} + D_1(n_3 + 2n_2C_2 + Y_4 + C_2Y_2^2) \\ &\quad + (n_4 + 2n_3C_2 + n_2(3C_3 - 2C_2^2) + Y_{5,1}) + D_2(n_3 + 2n_2C_2 + Y_4 + C_2Y_2^2) + D_3(n_2 + Y_3) + D_4Y_2)e_k^6) \\ &= -((n_2 + D_1Y_2)e_k^3 + (n_3 + 2n_2C_2 + C_2Y_2^2 + D_1(n_2 + Y_3) + D_2Y_2)e_k^4 \\ &\quad + (n_4 + 2n_3C_2 + n_2(3C_3 - 2C_2^2) + Y_{5,1} - Y_5 + D_1(n_3 + 2n_2C_2 + Y_4 + C_2Y_2^2) + D_2(n_2 + Y_3) + D_3Y_2)e_k^5 \\ &\quad + (n_5 + 2n_4C_2 + n_3(3C_3 - 2C_2^2) + n_2(Y_4 + C_2Y_2Y_2 + C_4) + Y_{6,1} - Y_6 + D_1(n_3 + 2n_2C_2 + Y_4 + C_2Y_2^2) \\ &\quad + (n_4 + 2n_3C_2 + n_2(3C_3 - 2C_2^2) + Y_{5,1}) + D_2(n_3 + 2n_2C_2 + Y_4 + C_2Y_2^2) + D_3(n_2 + Y_3) + D_4Y_2)e_k^6) \end{aligned}$$

$$= Z_3 e_k^3 + Z_4 e_k^4 + Z_5 e_k^5 + Z_6 e_k^6 + O(e_k^7),$$

where

$$Z_3 = -(n_2 + D_1 Y_2) = 0,$$

$$Z_4 = n_2 C_2 - 2n_3 + 4C_2 C_3 + 3C_3 C_2 - 9C_2^3,$$

$$Z_5 = 2n_2 C_3 + n_3 C_2 - 2n_4 + 6C_2 C_4 + 6C_3^2 + 4C_4 C_2 - 18C_2^2 C_3 - 14C_2 C_3 C_2 - 12C_3 C_2^2 + 30C_2^4,$$

$$Z_6 = 3n_2 C_4 + 2n_3 C_3 + n_4 C_2 - 2n_5 + 8C_2 C_5 + 9C_3 C_4 + 8C_4 C_3 + 5C_5 C_2 - 5n_2 C_2^3 - 27C_2^2 C_4 - 28C_2 C_3^2 - 19C_2 C_4 C_2 - 24C_3 C_2 C_3 - 18C_3^2 C_2 - 16C_4 C_2^2 + 60C_2^3 C_3 + 47C_2^2 C_3 C_2 + 43C_2 C_3 C_2^2 + 38C_3 C_2^3 - 88C_2^5,$$

demonstrating fourth-order convergence for the second step.

Similarly, we expand the accelerating factors α_k , β_k and δ_k ,

$$\alpha_k = \frac{F(y^{(k)})^T F(z^{(k)})}{F(x^{(k)})^T F(x^{(k)})} = a_4 e_k^4 + a_5 e_k^5 + a_6 e_k^6 + O(e_k^5),$$

where

$$a_4 = C_2 Z_4,$$

$$a_5 = -P^{-1} Q C_2 Z_4 + Y_3 Z_4 + C_2 Z_5,$$

$$a_6 = P^{-1} Q^2 C_2 Z_4 - P^{-1} R C_2 Z_4 + \frac{1}{2} P^{-1} Q C_2^2 Z_4 - P^{-1} Q Y_3 Z_4 + Y_4 Z_4 - P^{-1} Q C_2 Z_5 + Y_3 Z_5 + C_2 Z_6,$$

also

$$\delta_k = \frac{F(z^{(k)})^T F(z^{(k)})}{F(x^{(k)})^T F(x^{(k)})} = d_6 e_k^6 + O(e_k^7),$$

being

$$d_6 = Z_4^2 = 4(P^{-1})^2 Q^2 C_2^4 - 2(P^{-1}) Q C_2^2 C_3 C_2 - 2(P^{-1}) Q C_3 C_2^3 + C_3 C_2 C_3 C_2,$$

and

$$\beta_k = \frac{F(z^{(k)})^T F(z^{(k)})}{F(y^{(k)})^T F(y^{(k)})} = b_4 e_k^4 + b_5 e_k^5 + O(e_k^6),$$

where

$$b_4 = \frac{d_6}{C_2^2} = 4(P^{-1})^2 Q^2 C_2^2 - 2(P^{-1}) Q C_3 C_2 - 2(P^{-1}) Q C_3 C_2 + \frac{C_3 C_2 C_3 C_2}{C_2^2},$$

$$b_5 = \frac{Z_4 Z_5 + Z_5 Z_4}{C_2^2} - 2 \frac{Z_4^2}{C_2^4} (C_3 C_2 + C_2 C_3) + 4 \frac{Z_4^2 C_2^3}{C_2^4}.$$

In order to calculate the error equation we first simplify the expansion of the last factor in third step:

$$\begin{aligned} F(z^{(k)}) + (2\alpha_k(1 - \nu_k) + 4\delta_k) F(x^{(k)}) + (2\alpha_k + \beta_k) F(y^{(k)}) &= F'(\alpha) e_{z,k} + (2a_4 e_k^4 + 2a_5 e_k^5 + (2a_6 - 2a_4 n_2 + 4d_6) e_k^6) F(x^{(k)}) \\ &\quad + ((2a_4 + b_4) e_k^4 + (2a_5 + b_5) e_k^5) F(y^{(k)}) \\ &= F'(\alpha) e_{z,k} + F'(\alpha) (2a_4 e_k^5 + (2a_4 C_2 + 2a_5 + (2a_4 + b_4) Y_2) e_k^6 \\ &\quad + (2a_4 C_3 + 2a_5 C_2 + 2a_6 - 2a_4 n_2 + 4d_6 + (2a_4 + b_4) Y_3 \\ &\quad + (2a_5 + b_5) Y_2) e_k^7) + O(e_k^8). \end{aligned}$$

By replacing $Y_2 = C_2$, $n_2 = C_2^2$ e $Y_3 = 2C_3 - 2C_2^2$, then

$$\begin{aligned} F(z^{(k)}) + (2\alpha_k(1 - \nu_k) + 4\delta_k) F(x^{(k)}) + (2\alpha_k + \beta_k) F(y^{(k)}) &= F'(\alpha) e_{z,k} + F'(\alpha) (2a_4 e_k^5 + (4a_4 C_2 + 2a_5 + b_4 C_2) e_k^6 \\ &\quad + (2a_6 + 4a_5 C_2 + b_5 C_2 + 6a_4 C_3 + 2b_4 C_3 + 4d_6 - 2a_4 n_2 \\ &\quad - 4a_4 C_2^2 - 2b_4 C_2^2) e_k^7) + O(e_k^8). \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, by defining

$$r_5 = 2a_4,$$

$$r_6 = 2a_5 + (4a_4 + b_4) C_2,$$

$$r_7 = 2a_6 + 4d_6 + (4a_5 + b_5)C_2 + (6a_4 + 2b_4)(C_3 - C_2^2),$$

we set

$$F(z^{(k)}) + (2\alpha_k(1 - \nu_k) + 4\delta_k) F(x^{(k)}) + (2\alpha_k + \beta_k)F(y^{(k)}) = F'(\alpha)e_{z,k} + F'(\alpha) (r_5e_k^5 + r_6e_k^6 + r_7e_k^7) + O(e_k^8),$$

and then,

$$\begin{aligned} e_{k+1} &= e_{z,k} - [F'(x^{(k)})]^{-1} (F'(\alpha)e_{z,k} + F'(\alpha) (r_5e_k^5 + r_6e_k^6 + r_7e_k^7)) + O(e_k^8) \\ &= e_{z,k} - (I + D_1e_k + D_2e_k^2 + D_3e_k^3) (e_{z,k} + (r_5e_k^5 + r_6e_k^6 + r_7e_k^7)) + O(e_k^8) \\ &= -((r_5 + D_1Z_4)e_k^5 + (r_6 + D_1r_5 + D_1Z_5 + D_2Z_4)e_k^6 + (r_7 + D_1r_6 + D_2r_5 + D_1Z_6 + D_2Z_5 + D_3Z_4)e_k^7) + O(e_k^8) \\ &= -(r_5 + D_1Z_4)e_k^5 - (r_6 + D_1r_5 + D_1Z_5 + D_2Z_4)e_k^6 - (r_7 + D_1r_6 + D_2r_5 + D_1Z_6 + D_2Z_5 + D_3Z_4)e_k^7 + O(e_k^8). \end{aligned}$$

If we group the coefficients of the different powers of the error,

$$J_5 = r_5 + D_1Z_4,$$

$$J_6 = r_6 + D_1r_5 + D_1Z_5 + D_2Z_4,$$

$$J_7 = r_7 + D_1r_6 + D_2r_5 + D_1Z_6 + D_2Z_5 + D_3Z_4,$$

we can find that they are null:

$$J_5 = r_5 + D_1Z_4 = 2a_4 + D_1Z_4 = 2C_2Z_4 + D_1Z_4 = 2C_2Z_4 - 2C_2Z_4 = 0,$$

also

$$\begin{aligned} J_6 &= r_6 + D_1r_5 + D_1Z_5 + D_2Z_4 = 4a_4C_2 + 2a_5 + b_4C_2 + 2D_1a_4 + D_1Z_5 + D_2Z_4 \\ &= 4a_4C_2 + 2a_5 + b_4C_2 - 4a_4C_2 - 2C_2Z_5 - 3C_3Z_4 + 4C_2^2Z_4 \\ &= -4C_2^2Z_4 + 2Y_3Z_4 + 2C_2Z_5 + b_4C_2 - 2C_2Z_5 - 3C_3Z_4 + 4C_2^2Z_4 \\ &= 2(2C_3 - 2C_2^2)Z_4 + \frac{Z_4^4}{C_2^2}C_2 - 3C_3Z_4 \\ &= \left(C_3 - 4C_2^2 + \frac{Z_4C_2}{C_2^2} \right) Z_4 \\ &= (C_3 - 4C_2^2 + \frac{C_2^2C_2^2 - 4C_2C_3C_2 - 4C_3C_2^2 + 12C_2^4 + 4C_2C_3C_2 + 3C_3C_2^2 - 9C_2^4}{C_2^2})Z_4 \\ &= (C_3 - 4C_2^2 + \frac{-C_3C_2^2 + 4C_2^4}{C_2^2})Z_4 = 0, \end{aligned}$$

and finally,

$$\begin{aligned} J_7 &= r_7 + D_1r_6 + D_2r_5 + D_1Z_6 + D_2Z_5 + D_3Z_4 \\ &= (2(P^{-1})^2Q^2C_2 - 2P^{-1}RC_2 + P^{-1}QC_2^2 - 2P^{-1}QY_3 + 2Y_4 - 4C_4 + 6C_2C_3 + 6C_3C_2 - 14C_2^3) Z_4 \\ &\quad + b_5C_2 + 2b_4C_3 + (-2P^{-1}QC_2 + 2Y_3 - 3C_3 + 4C_2^2) Z_5 \\ &= (2(P^{-1})^2Q^2C_2 - 2P^{-1}RC_2 + P^{-1}QC_2^2 - 2P^{-1}Q(2C_3 - 2C_2^2) + 2C_4 - 2C_2C_3 - 6C_2^3) Z_4 \\ &\quad + b_5C_2 + 2b_4C_3 + (-2P^{-1}QC_2 + 2(2C_3 - 2C_2^2) - 3C_3 + 4C_2^2) Z_5 \\ &= (2(P^{-1})^2Q^2C_2 - 2P^{-1}RC_2 + 5P^{-1}QC_2^2 - 4P^{-1}QC_3 \\ &\quad + 2C_4 - 2C_2C_3 - 6C_2^3) Z_4 + b_5C_2 + 2b_4C_3 + (C_3 - 2P^{-1}QC_2)Z_5 \\ &= \left(2(P^{-1})^2Q^2C_2 - 2P^{-1}RC_2 + 5P^{-1}QC_2^2 - 4P^{-1}QC_3 + 2C_4 - 2C_2C_3 - 6C_2^3 + 4Z_4 - 2 - 2\frac{Z_4C_3}{C_2^2} + \frac{Z_5C_2}{C_2^2} \right) Z_4 \\ &\quad + (C_3 - 2P^{-1}QC_2 + \frac{Z_4C_2}{C_2^2})Z_5 \\ &= \left(-6P^{-1}QC_2^2 + 4P^{-1}QC_3 + 4Z_4 - 2\frac{Z_4C_3}{C_2^2} - \frac{2C_3^2C_2}{C_2^2} - 4C_2^3 + 4C_3C_2 \right) Z_4 + \left(C_3 - 2P^{-1}QC_2 + \frac{Z_4C_2}{C_2^2} \right) Z_5 \end{aligned}$$

$$= \left(2P^{-1}QC_2^2 - 2\frac{-C_3C_2C_3}{C_2^2} - \frac{2C_3^2C_2}{C_2^2} - 4C_2^3 \right) Z_4.$$

Let us remark that the factors coming from the scalar accelerators $\alpha_k, \beta_k, \delta_k$ and ν_k are commutative. So, $2\frac{C_3C_2C_3}{C_2^2} = 2\frac{C_3C_3C_2}{C_2^2} = 2\frac{C_3^2C_2}{C_2^2}$. On the other hand, let us recall that $Q = PC_2 + C_2P$, yielding $P^{-1}Q = C_2 + P^{-1}C_2P$, where the last summand is also scalar.

Therefore, $P^{-1}Q = C_2 + C_2 = 2C_2$.

By using these relations, we conclude that $J_7 = 0$, so the optimal eighth-order of convergence (in the sense of Conjecture 1) is proven. \square

3. Complex dynamics

The study of an iterative method as a complex discrete dynamical system allows us to classify the iterative procedures by analyzing their behavior according to the seed used. This analysis provides a visual representation of the performance of the method, as it allows visualizing the solutions and the domain of the seeds allowing convergence. Furthermore, it allows us to deduce key information on the reliability and stability of the scheme.

In this section, we aim to study the complex dynamics of the method (3) for low-degree polynomials of the form $p(x) = (x - a)(x - b)$, being a, b complex numbers. To extend the obtained results to other second-degree polynomials, it is necessary to prove the following Scaling Theorem, as it allows us to relate the dynamical behavior of one operator to another.

Theorem 2. *Let us consider an analytical function $f(x)$ defined on the Riemann sphere, and also an affine transformation $T(x) = \alpha x + \beta$, for $\alpha \neq 0$. Considering $g(x) = \lambda(f \circ T)(x)$, $\lambda \neq 0$, let R_f and R_g be the fixed point functions of scheme (3) related, respectively, to f and g . In other words,*

$$R_f(x) = z_f - \frac{f(z_f) + (2\alpha_f(1 - \nu_f) + 4\delta_f) f(x) + (2\alpha_f + \beta_f)f(y_f)}{f'(x)}, \tag{4}$$

$$R_g(x) = z_g - \frac{g(z_g) + (2\alpha_g(1 - \nu_g) + 4\delta_g) g(x) + (2\alpha_g + \beta_g)g(y_g)}{g'(x)}, \tag{5}$$

being $y_f = x - \frac{f(x)}{f'(x)}$, $z_f = y_f - \frac{(1 + \nu_f)f(y_f) + 2\nu_f f(x)}{f'(x)}$, $y_g = x - \frac{g(x)}{g'(x)}$, $z_g = y_g - \frac{(1 + \nu_g)g(y_g) + 2\nu_g g(x)}{g'(x)}$, $x \in \mathbb{C}$ and

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{ll} \nu_f = \frac{f(y_f)^2}{f(x)^2}, & \alpha_f = \frac{f(y_f)f(z_f)}{f(x)^2}, \\ \beta_f = \frac{f(z_f)^2}{f(y_f)^2}, & \delta_f = \frac{f(z_f)^2}{f(x)^2}, \\ \nu_g = \frac{g(y_g)^2}{g(x)^2}, & \alpha_g = \frac{g(y_g)g(z_g)}{g(x)^2}, \\ \beta_g = \frac{g(z_g)^2}{g(y_g)^2}, & \delta_g = \frac{g(z_g)^2}{g(x)^2}. \end{array} \right.$$

Then, R_f is conjugate to R_g via T ,

$$(T \circ R_g \circ T^{-1})(x) = R_f(x).$$

Proof. Considering that $T(w - k) = T(w) - T(k) + \beta$, $T(w + k) = T(w) + T(k) - \beta$ and $g'(x) = \alpha\lambda f'(T(x))$, then

$$T(T^{-1}(y_g)) = T\left(T^{-1}(x) - \frac{g(T^{-1}(x))}{g'(T^{-1}(x))}\right) = T\left(T^{-1}(x) - \frac{f(x)}{\alpha f'(x)}\right) = x - T\left(\frac{f(x)}{\alpha f'(x)}\right) + \beta = x - \frac{f(x)}{f'(x)} = y_f.$$

On the other hand,

$$\nu_g(T^{-1}) = \frac{g(T^{-1}(y_g))^2}{g(T^{-1}(x))^2} = \frac{(\lambda f(T(T^{-1}(y_g))))^2}{(\lambda f(T(T^{-1}(x))))^2} = \frac{f(y_f)^2}{f(x)^2} = \nu_f,$$

thus $\nu_g(T^{-1}) = \nu_f$.

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} T(T^{-1}(z_g)) &= T\left(T^{-1}(y_g) - \frac{(1 + v_g(T^{-1}))g(T^{-1}(y_g)) + 2v_g g(T^{-1}(x))}{g'(T^{-1}(x))}\right) \\ &= T\left(T^{-1}(y_g) - \frac{(1 + v_f)g(T^{-1}(y_g)) + 2v_f g(T^{-1}(x))}{\alpha \lambda f'(x)}\right) \\ &= y_f - T\left(\frac{(1 + v_f)\lambda f(y_f) + 2v_f \lambda f(x)}{\alpha \lambda f'(x)}\right) + \beta \\ &= y_f - \alpha\left(\frac{(1 + v_f)f(y_f) + 2v_f f(x)}{\alpha f'(x)}\right) - \beta + \beta = z_f. \end{aligned}$$

In an analogous way to how we proved that $v_g(T^{-1}) = v_f$, we can also prove $\alpha_g(T^{-1}) = \alpha_f$, $\beta_g(T^{-1}) = \beta_f$ and $\delta_g(T^{-1}) = \delta_f$. Now, let us demonstrate that R_f is analytically conjugate to R_g via T .

$$\begin{aligned} (T \circ R_g \circ T^{-1})(x) &= T(R_g(T^{-1}(x))) = \\ &= T\left(T^{-1}(z_g) - \frac{g(T^{-1}(z_g)) + (2\alpha_g(T^{-1})(1 - v_g(T^{-1})) + 4\delta_g(T^{-1}))g(T^{-1}(x)) + (2\alpha_g(T^{-1}) + \beta_g(T^{-1}))g(T^{-1}(y_g))}{g'(T^{-1}(x))}\right) = \\ &= T\left(T^{-1}(z_g) - \frac{g(T^{-1}(z_g)) + (2\alpha_f(1 - v_f) + 4\delta_f)g(T^{-1}(x)) + (2\alpha_f + \beta_f)g(T^{-1}(y_g))}{g'(T^{-1}(x))}\right) \\ &= T\left(T^{-1}(z_g) - \frac{\lambda f(z_f) + (2\alpha_f(1 - v_f) + 4\delta_f)\lambda f(x) + (2\alpha_f + \beta_f)\lambda f(y_f)}{\alpha \lambda f'(x)}\right) \\ &= T\left(T^{-1}(z_g) - \frac{f(z_f) + (2\alpha_f(1 - v_f) + 4\delta_f)f(x) + (2\alpha_f + \beta_f)f(y_f)}{\alpha f'(x)}\right) \\ &= T(T^{-1}(z_g)) - T\left(\frac{f(z_f) + (2\alpha_f(1 - v_f) + 4\delta_f)f(x) + (2\alpha_f + \beta_f)f(y_f)}{\alpha f'(x)}\right) + \beta \\ &= z_f - \alpha\left(\frac{f(z_f) + (2\alpha_f(1 - v_f) + 4\delta_f)f(x) + (2\alpha_f + \beta_f)f(y_f)}{\alpha f'(x)}\right) - \beta + \beta \\ &= z_f - \left(\frac{f(z_f) + (2\alpha_f(1 - v_f) + 4\delta_f)f(x) + (2\alpha_f + \beta_f)f(y_f)}{f'(x)}\right) = R_f(x), \end{aligned}$$

then $(T \circ R_g \circ T^{-1})(x) = R_f(x)$, i.e., R_f and R_g are analytically conjugate via $T(x)$. \square

By applying the Möbius transformation on the rational operator related to the iterative scheme (3), we obtain a conjugate operator that does not depend on a and b . The map used is $h(x) = \frac{x-a}{x-b}$, which has the following properties, which maps a to 0, b to ∞ , and the divergence of the original iterative method to 1,

$$\text{i) } h(\infty) = 1 \quad \text{ii) } h(a) = 0 \quad \text{i) } h(b) = \infty.$$

So, the conjugated operator that we obtain is as follows

$$O(x) = (h \circ R_p \circ h^{-1})(x) = \frac{x^8 n(x)}{d(x)}, \tag{6}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} n(x) &= x^{22} + 28x^{21} + 377x^{20} + 3248x^{19} + 20097x^{18} + 95004x^{17} + 356265x^{16} + 1085760x^{15} + 2731509x^{14} \\ &\quad + 5725868x^{13} + 10044373x^{12} + 14745138x^{11} + 18046707x^{10} + 18287868x^9 + 15197466x^8 + 10233318x^7 \\ &\quad + 5502621x^6 + 2319888x^5 + 748062x^4 + 177858x^3 + 29368x^2 + 3008x + 144, \\ d(x) &= 144x^{22} + 3008x^{21} + 29368x^{20} + 177858x^{19} + 748062x^{18} + 2319888x^{17} + 5502621x^{16} + 10233318x^{15} \\ &\quad + 15197466x^{14} + 18287868x^{13} + 18046707x^{12} + 14745138x^{11} + 10044373x^{10} + 5725868x^9 + 2731509x^8 \\ &\quad + 1085760x^7 + 356265x^6 + 95004x^5 + 20097x^4 + 3248x^3 + 377x^2 + 28x + 1. \end{aligned}$$

We can easily deduce from the power of x in (6), that the convergence order of the scheme for second-degree polynomials is 8. On the other hand, it is known [10] that a fixed point of O is an invariant point by O , that is, a point satisfying $O(x) = x$. All the roots of $p(x)$ (in fact, their mapped points by h) will be fixed points of the rational operator O , but they cannot be the only ones. It may happen that there appear fixed points not corresponding to any root, known as strange fixed points. They are not desirable from the numerical point of view, since if a seed is considered in its vicinity, the numerical method may converge to it. Therefore, we need to analyze the stability character of strange fixed points to show the general dependence of the method of the seeds used.

The stability of the fixed points depends on $O'(x)$. A fixed point x^* is:

- Repelling, if $|O'(x^*)| > 1$;
- Attracting, if $|O'(x^*)| < 1$;
- Parabolic, if $|O'(x^*)| = 1$;
- Superattracting, if $|O'(x^*)| = 0$.

We now study specifically the stability of the fixed points of O .

Theorem 3. *The fixed points of rational operator O are determined by solving the equation $O(x) = x$. Then,*

- $x = 1$ is a repelling strange fixed point.
- $x = 0$ and $x = \infty$ are superattracting fixed points.
- 28 real or complex roots of polynomial $k(t)$

$$\begin{aligned}
 k(t) = & 1 + 29t + 406t^2 + 3654t^3 + 23751t^4 + 118755t^5 + 475020t^6 + 1560636t^7 + 4289137t^8 \\
 & + 9985637t^9 + 19852152t^{10} + 33849228t^{11} + 49576047t^{12} + 62361294t^{13} + 67325442t^{14} \\
 & + 62361294t^{15} + 49576047t^{16} + 33849228t^{17} + 19852152t^{18} + 9985637t^{19} + 4289137t^{20} \\
 & + 1560636t^{21} + 475020t^{22} + 118755t^{23} + 23751t^{24} + 3654t^{25} + 406t^{26} + 29t^{27} + t^{28},
 \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

denoted by E_i , $i = 1, \dots, 28$, are strange fixed points with repelling character.

Proof. To find the fixed points of operator O , we solve the equation $O(x) = x$, obtaining

$$x(x - 1)k(x) = 0,$$

thus, the fixed points of the rational operator $O(x)$ are $x = 0$ (and $x = \infty$, by conjugation), $x = 1$ and the roots of polynomial $k(x)$. By definition, to analyze the stability of these fixed points, we need the derivative of operator O ,

$$O'(x) = \frac{2x^7(x + 1)^{28}m(x)}{(d(x))^2},$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
 m(x) = & 576x^{16} + 11520x^{15} + 106312x^{14} + 598651x^{13} + 2292040x^{12} + 6296055x^{11} + 12772473x^{10} \\
 & + 19432239x^9 + 22334244x^8 + 19432239x^7 + 12772473x^6 + 6296055x^5 + 2292040x^4 + 598651x^3 \\
 & + 106312x^2 + 11520x + 576.
 \end{aligned}$$

It is clear that 0 and ∞ are always superattractors, as they are related to the roots of $p(x)$ and the convergence order of the method is greater than two (also, $O'(0) = 0$). Therefore, we will now analyze the nature of the strange fixed points. We obtain that

$$|O'(1)| = \frac{67108864}{13169247} > 1$$

therefore $z = 1$ is a repelling strange fixed point. Similarly, we establish that the roots of the polynomial $k(x)$ (7) are also repelling strange fixed points. \square

This result proves that method CTT (3) is stable and that the roots of $p(x)$ are the only superattracting fixed points. As a complementary tool of the complex dynamical analysis, we represent the dynamic plane to visually illustrate the behavior of the method. The algorithm employed to generate in Matlab the dynamical plane is similar to those appearing in [11]. Every point of a mesh in the plane is considered as a complex initial estimation z and it is represented using different colors depending on the point it converges to.

The dynamical plane presented in Fig. 1 has been defined with a meshgrid of 800×800 points and an upper bound of 100 iterations. The superattracting fixed points are identified by a white star and fixed points are represented as white circles. We represent in orange color those points converging to the root 0. Those points tending to infinity appear in blue, and black color corresponds to the non-converging points.

Fig. 1. Dynamical plane of method CTT (3).

We observe that there are no black regions. Moreover, all fixed points other than the roots of the polynomial (represented by circles) are on the boundary (called the Julia set) and are therefore repulsive fixed points.

4. Efficiency

For a rigorous comparative evaluation of various iterative methods, from the point of view of computational cost, the Ostrowski efficiency index is usually used. This index is mathematically expressed as:

$$I = p^{1/d},$$

where p represents the order of convergence and d denotes the number of function evaluations per iteration.

Additionally, the computational efficiency index is also employed

$$IC = p^{1/(d+op)},$$

with op signifying the number of operations per iteration, and provides a complementary measure.

In this section, we undertake a comparative analysis of the efficiency indices of the proposed method CTT (3), and several existing methods exhibiting comparable or higher orders of convergence. This analysis considers the impact of varying system sizes, denoted by n , on the efficiency of each method.

The proposed method will be compared against the following established methods from the literature: PM defined by Behl et al. in [12], M_9 defined by Xiao et al. in [13] and WYQ defined by Wang et al. in [14].

It is crucial to note that a single evaluation of the function F yields n evaluations of its scalar coordinate functions $f_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, n$. Similarly, evaluating the derivative operator F' implies n^2 scalar evaluations of the respective partial derivatives of each f_i .

Furthermore, the computational cost associated with matrix-vector products, linear system solutions, and scalar/vector/matrix multiplications within each iteration of the iterative expression must be carefully considered. The following catalog summarizes the number of products and quotients required for the operations involved:

- Each transpose vector/vector product costs n .
- Each scalar/vector product costs n .
- Each matrix/matrix product costs n^3 .
- Each matrix/vector product costs n^2 .
- Each LU decomposition costs $\frac{1}{3}(n^3 - n)$.
- Each system resolution costs n^2 .

In the case of the iterative scheme CTT (3), we need $F(x^{(k)})$, $F(y^{(k)})$, $F(z^{(k)})$ and just one Jacobian matrix, so the evaluations of F are

$$3n + n^2 = n^2 + 3n.$$

Also, in the iterative scheme CTT (3), we calculate four vector/scalar products, four transposed vector/vector multiplications, one LU decomposition and solve three linear systems, so the operations are

$$4n + 4n + \frac{1}{3}(n^3 - n) + 3n^2 = \frac{1}{3}(n^3 - n) + 3n^2 + 8n.$$

Therefore, the amount of operations and evaluations is:

$$\frac{1}{3}(n^3 - n) + 3n^2 + 8n + n^2 + 3n = \frac{1}{3}(n^3 - n) + 4n^2 + 11n,$$

and therefore the efficiency index of the scheme CTT is

$$I_{CTT} = 8^{1/(n^2 + 3n)},$$

and its computational efficiency index is

$$IC_{CTT} = 8^{1/(\frac{1}{3}(n^3 - n) + 4n^2 + 11n)}.$$

Let us now calculate the corresponding indices of other high-order methods. First, we consider scheme *PM* defined by Behl et al. in [12], with order of convergence 9 and iterative expression:

$$\begin{cases} y_1^{(k)} &= x^{(k)} - [F'(x^{(k)})]^{-1} F(x^{(k)}), \quad k = 0, 1, 2, \dots, \\ y_2^{(k)} &= x^{(k)} - 2 [F'(x^{(k)}) + F'(y_1^{(k)})]^{-1} F(x^{(k)}), \\ y_3^{(k)} &= y_2^{(k)} - [3F'(y_1^{(k)}) - F'(x^{(k)})]^{-1} (F'(y_1^{(k)}) + F'(x^{(k)})) [F'(x^{(k)})]^{-1} (F(y_2^{(k)})), \\ x^{(k+1)} &= y_3^{(k)} - [3F'(y_1^{(k)}) - F'(x^{(k)})]^{-1} (F'(y_1^{(k)}) + F'(x^{(k)})) [F'(x^{(k)})]^{-1} (F(y_3^{(k)})). \end{cases} \tag{8}$$

Per iteration, the *PM* method evaluates two Jacobian matrices ($F'(x)$, $F'(y_1)$) and three vectorial functions ($F(x)$, $F(y_2)$ and $F(y_3)$). So, the total amount of functional evaluations is $2n^2 + 3n$. Regarding the rest of computational effort, in each iteration of the *PM* procedure, it should:

- solve 3 linear systems with coefficient matrix $F'(x^{(k)})$, one with coefficient matrix $F'(x^{(k)}) + F'(y_1^{(k)})$ and another two with $3F'(y_1^{(k)}) - F'(x^{(k)})$.
- Moreover, there are two matrix/vector products in the third and fourth steps, one scalar/vector product in the second step and the same scalar/matrix product $3F'(y_1^{(k)})$ in the third and fourth step.

So, the efficiency index of the *PM* procedure is

$$I_{PM} = 9^{1/(2n^2 + 3n)},$$

and its computational efficiency index is

$$IC_{PM} = 9^{1/(n^3 + 11n^2 + 3n)}.$$

We also compare our proposal with scheme M_9 , designed by Xiao in [13], with ninth-order of convergence. Its iterative expression is:

$$\begin{cases} y^{(k)} &= x^{(k)} - [F'(x^{(k)})]^{-1} F(x^{(k)}), \quad k = 0, 1, 2, \dots, \\ z^{(k)} &= x^{(k)} - \frac{1}{2} [F'(x^{(k)})^{-1} + F'(y^{(k)})^{-1}] F(x^{(k)}), \\ w^{(k)} &= z^{(k)} - \left[-F'(x^{(k)})^{-1} + \frac{3}{2} F'(y^{(k)})^{-1} + \frac{1}{2} F'(x^{(k)})^{-1} F'(y^{(k)}) F'(x^{(k)})^{-1} \right] (F(z^{(k)})), \\ x^{(k+1)} &= w^{(k)} - \left[-F'(x^{(k)})^{-1} + \frac{3}{2} F'(y^{(k)})^{-1} + \frac{1}{2} F'(x^{(k)})^{-1} F'(y^{(k)}) F'(x^{(k)})^{-1} \right] (F(w^{(k)})). \end{cases} \tag{9}$$

As in previous cases, its efficiency is deduced from the amount of functional evaluations ($2n^2 + 3n$, due to 2 Jacobian matrices and 3 functions evaluated) and number of products/quotients, per iteration. The later ones are $\frac{2}{3}(n^3 - n) + 10n^2 + 5n$, due to 5 linear systems solved with $F'(x^{(k)})$ as coefficient matrix, 3 linear systems with $F'(y^{(k)})$ and also 2 matrix/vector and 5 scalar/vector products in the third and fourth steps. Therefore, the efficiency index of M_9 is

$$I_{M_9} = 9^{1/(2n^2 + 3n)},$$

and the computational index is

$$IC_{M_9} = 9^{1/(\frac{2}{3}(n^3 - n) + 12n^2 + 8n)}.$$

Fig. 2. Efficiency indices for different sizes of the system.

Moreover, Wang et al. in [14] constructed the eighth-order scheme WYQ ,

$$\begin{cases} y^{(k)} &= x^{(k)} - [F'(x^{(k)})]^{-1} F(x^{(k)}), \\ w^{(k)} &= y^{(k)} - \left(I + \left(I + \frac{5}{4} M^{(k)} \right) M^{(k)} \right) F'(x^{(k)})^{-1} (F(y^{(k)})), \\ x^{(k+1)} &= w^{(k)} - \left(I + \left(I + \frac{3}{2} M^{(k)} \right) M^{(k)} \right) F'(x^{(k)})^{-1} (F(w^{(k)})), \quad k = 0, 1, 2, \dots, \end{cases} \tag{10}$$

where $M^{(k)} = F'(x^{(k)})^{-1} (F'(x^{(k)}) - F'(y^{(k)}))$. To calculate the efficiency indices of WYQ , it must be taken into account that it needs two functional evaluations of matrices $F'(x^{(k)})$ and $F'(y^{(k)})$ and three of functions $F(x^{(k)})$, $F(y^{(k)})$ and $F(w^{(k)})$ ($2n^2 + 3n$ evaluations). Indeed, in each iteration, 7 linear systems with coefficient matrix $F'(x^{(k)})$ must be solved and the amount of matrix/vector and scalar/vector products is 4 and 2, respectively, in the second and third steps. This results in the efficiency index

$$I_{WYQ} = 8^1 / (2n^2 + 3n),$$

and the computational index

$$IC_{WYQ} = 8^1 / \left(\frac{1}{3}(n^3 - n) + 13n^2 + 5n \right).$$

In Figs. 2 and 3, we observe that CTT scheme shows the best indices for small and big-sized systems. This performance is maintained even when compared with recent ninth-order methods as PM and $M9$.

5. Numerical results

Now, we compare the numerical performance of our proposed optimal eighth-order vectorial scheme with those of the same existing eight- and ninth-order methods PM , $M9$ and WYQ that have been already used in the efficiency indices comparison.

For the computational calculations, we use Matlab R2022b with variable precision arithmetic of 1000 digits of mantissa. The maximum number of iterations considered is 50 and the stopping criterion is $\|x^{(k+1)} - x^{(k)}\| < 10^{-100}$ or $\|F(x^{(k+1)})\| < 10^{-100}$. The computer used has a processor Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-9700 CPU @ 3.00GHz 3.00 GHz, with a RAM of 32GB. The compared items in the different examples are:

- the norm of the non-linear function F defining the test system, evaluated at the last estimation of the solution,
- the norm of the distance between the last two approximations,
- the number of iterations necessary to satisfy the required tolerance,
- the computational time and the approximate computational convergence order (ACOC), defined by Cordero and Torregrosa in [15], which has the following expression

$$p \approx ACOC = \frac{\ln \left(\frac{\|x^{(k+1)} - x^{(k)}\|}{\|x^{(k)} - x^{(k-1)}\|} \right)}{\ln \left(\frac{\|x^{(k)} - x^{(k-1)}\|}{\|x^{(k-1)} - x^{(k-2)}\|} \right)},$$

- the mean CPU-time (in seconds) of 50 consecutive executions.

Fig. 3. Computational Efficiency indices for different sizes of the system.

Table 1
Results Example 1.

Method	CPU Time	Iterations	$\ x^{(k+1)} - x^{(k)}\ $	$\ F(x^{(k+1)})\ $	ACOC
Newton	44.3281	50	3.5236	52.145	-
PM	9.7438	4	8.4856×10^{-30}	1.9611×10^{-260}	-
M_9	9.3516	4	7.6622×10^{-28}	8.8849×10^{-243}	-
WYQ	7.8706	4	3.3445×10^{-22}	1.183×10^{-171}	-
CTT	7.2719	4	4.4023×10^{-28}	3.2269×10^{-243}	-

Table 2
Results Example 2.

Method	CPU Time	Iterations	$\ x^{(k+1)} - x^{(k)}\ $	$\ F(x^{(k+1)})\ $	ACOC
Newton	123.0122	14	1.5703×10^{-106}	3.401×10^{-121}	-
PM	111.594	4	1.597×10^{-63}	3.0208×10^{-110}	-
M_9	234.4344	7	7.8055×10^{-54}	8.4678×10^{-101}	7.7829
WYQ	110.5250	4	2.3691×10^{-67}	2.3214×10^{-118}	-
CTT	94.7141	4	9.1769×10^{-59}	1.8382×10^{-122}	7.2124

Example 1. We start with the system of m non-linear equations

$$x_i - 1.5 \sin \left(\sum_{j=1, j \neq i}^m x_j \right) = 0, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m,$$

with $m = 20$, whose solution is $\xi \approx (0.15973, 0.15973, \dots, 0.15973)^T$. We have used as seed $x^{(0)} = \left(\frac{1}{10}, \frac{1}{10}, \dots, \frac{1}{10}\right)^T$. As we observe in Table 1, the proposed eighth-order optimal vectorial scheme is able to find the required solution even faster than known ninth-order schemes with similar estimation of the error and the same number of iterations. Note that the ACOC is not stable for any of the methods used in this example.

Example 2. Our second example is defined by the non-linear system of m equations,

$$x_i - \cos \left(- \left(\sum_{j=1}^m x_j \right) + 2x_i \right) = 0, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m,$$

where $m = 100$. In this case, the searched solution is $\xi \approx (0.20625, 0.20625, \dots, 0.20625)^T$ and the initial estimation used in all the iterative schemes is $x^{(0)} = \left(\frac{1}{10}, \dots, \frac{1}{10}\right)^T$. The obtained results can be seen in Table 2. In it, the lowest execution time is featured again by CTT scheme, with also the lowest residual error, even compared with higher-order methods.

Table 3
Results Example 3.

Method	CPU Time	Iterations	$\ x^{(k+1)} - x^{(k)}\ $	$\ F(x^{(k+1)})\ $	ACOC
Newton	188.2344	9	6.2856×10^{-111}	5.3007×10^{-222}	2.0
PM	165.5594	3	9.7133×10^{-38}	9.5784×10^{-345}	9.416
M_9	156.4672	3	3.8226×10^{-27}	7.3265×10^{-248}	8.5096
WYQ	135.1391	3	2.9448×10^{-15}	1.5346×10^{-120}	6.8737
CTT	122.8766	3	2.904×10^{-16}	5.9932×10^{-132}	7.0544

Table 4
Results Example 4.

Method	CPU Time	Iterations	$\ x^{(k+1)} - x^{(k)}\ $	$\ F(x^{(k+1)})\ $	ACOC
Newton	3.3047	8	2.852×10^{-195}	1.4032×10^{-390}	2.0
PM	3.0016	3	1.3556×10^{-77}	3.7166×10^{-547}	7.1466
M_9	3.0250	3	3.636×10^{-75}	1.2309×10^{-529}	7.1455
WYQ	2.6406	3	2.8188×10^{-60}	1.0522×10^{-364}	6.1773
CTT	2.4984	3	7.0044×10^{-26}	1.0731×10^{-105}	4.0481

Example 3. Another big-sized non-linear system is given by

$$x_i^2 x_{i+1} - 1 = 0, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m - 1,$$

$$x_m^2 x_1 - 1 = 0,$$

for $m = 500$, whose solution is $\xi \approx (1, 1, \dots, 1)^T$ and $x^{(0)} = \left(\frac{3}{2}, \dots, \frac{3}{2}\right)^T$ is the initial guess used. In Table 3, the previous situation is observed, corresponding to CTT scheme the lowest computational time. These results again confirm the results obtained in the efficiency analysis, being the numerical estimations of the order of convergence a rough approximation, due to the few iterations needed to converge.

Example 4. As a final test, we approach the problem of an integral equation of Hammerstein-type (for further information, please see the text of Ortega and Rheinboldt, [16]), whose expression is

$$u(s) = 1 + \frac{1}{5} \int_0^1 K(s, t) u(t)^3 dt,$$

being $u \in C([0, 1])$, t and s belong to the interval $[0, 1]$ and the Kernel K is defined as

$$K(s, t) = \begin{cases} t(1 - s) & \text{if } t \leq s, \\ (1 - t)s & \text{if } s < t. \end{cases}$$

We use a Gauss-Legendre quadrature with $n = 7$ nodes t_i and weights w_i , for $i = 1, 2, \dots, 7$, in order to transform this problem in a system of non-linear equations,

$$-5 + 5u_i - \sum_{k=1}^7 c_{i,k} u_k^3 = 0,$$

where u_i denotes $u(t_i)$, for $i = 1, 2, \dots, 7$, and

$$c_{i,k} = \begin{cases} w_k t_k (1 - t_i) & \text{if } k \leq i, \\ w_k t_i (1 - t_k) & \text{if } i < k. \end{cases}$$

The initial estimation used is $x^{(0)} = (0.5, \dots, 0.5)^T$, with the same tolerance and digits as in the previous examples. It can be observed in Table 4 that the results provided by the proposed scheme highly improve the results obtained by the known schemes, with a lower execution time than them. Except for Newton’s method, the ACOC in the rest of the schemes is below the established theoretical order.

6. Outcomes and conclusions

In this manuscript, the only eighth-order optimal iterative scheme for systems of non-linear equations, according to the Optimality Conjecture, has been designed. Its computational efficiency highly improves the results obtained by known methods, even of the ninth order of convergence, for small and large systems. Moreover, CTT shows good stability properties, with global convergence to the roots on quadratic polynomials. The numerical tests performed, even for big problems, show this efficient performance of the proposed

class, with low CPU-times. This fact is of special relevance, as usually Newton's vectorial scheme is better in terms of computational time than the higher-order scheme, but it is not true for optimal vectorial methods, as has been demonstrated. In future work, our aim is to explore the development of optimal iterative methods for nonlinear systems, including both extensions of the current procedure to orders greater than 8 and the creation of innovative schemes.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

All authors contributed equally to this manuscript.

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Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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